

CDNOT Node Storage Survey

CMIP International Project Office April 2026

The Climate Data Node Operations Team (CDNOT) in partnership with the CMIP IPO and WCRP ESMO Infrastructure Panel (WIP) conducted a short survey of ESGF node information via Jotform commencing February 10th 2026.

Responses were collected until 01 April 2026. The aim was to find out about node storage, specifically for CMIP7 and CORDEX CMIP6. Repeated requests were made to the nodes via the ESGF Slack and CDNOT community mailing list to complete the survey. In total, sixteen nodes responded to the Jotform survey, with additional two nodes providing information afterwards on CORDEX only.

The data collected here also include cross-referenced responses from a separate CORDEX survey conducted in March and April 2026 and provided courtesy of the CORDEX -TTPI.

Data were processed in Airtable and can be viewed at: <https://airtable.com/applbQctZtl09L2Ga/shrkWp4nKGbPDQGYG>

Summary

- **Majority of nodes** are publication only for modelling centres (62%). Only five nodes provide publication **and** replication.
- USA, France and Australia are the **top-three country nodes** in terms of total storage, with 20, 12 and 3.3 PB respectively. As the West index node in NG, **USA stands out** in terms of available current and projected storage for CMIP and CORDEX data.
- **73% of nodes have less** than 1 PB total storage. Only half of the responding nodes have emergency storage available, the majority less than 0.5 PB.
- Of the five country nodes hosting **CMIP6 and CMIP6Plus**, only Australia, USA and France have more than 1 PB of storage.
- Ten nodes have planned storage for **CMIP7** data with a 50/50 split between those having more than 1 PB and less than 1 PB available.
- Eight nodes have less than 0.5 PB of **CORDEX CMIP5** storage.
- For **CORDEX CMIP6**, eight nodes have provision for storage, and three nodes plan greater than 1 PB of storage.
- Only four nodes have provision for **CORDEX CMIP7 AFT** and all have less than 0.4 PB planned storage.
- Half of the nodes responding to the survey **have less** than 0.5 FTE in terms of staff resources.
- **Near-Term Risks** — funding and staff/resources are the most prominent concerns for node administrators, alongside hardware provisioning and delayed timelines for hardware installation.
- **Capacity for WCRP Projects** — government funding and specific storage targets stand out, with the ESGF-NG node construction and grant proposals for national infrastructure as key themes.
- **CORDEX comments** — Mainly around storage scales (available space to host CORDEX projects) with ESGF-NG publication and again, node funding as recurring themes.

CMIP6 and CMIP7 storage

Type of node responding to the survey

- Publication and Replication (5)
- Publication for modelling centre (10)
- Replication only (1)

Total storage by country in Petabytes (PB)

Flexible storage > 20 PB

Emergency storage by country in Petabytes (PB)

CMIP6 current and projected storage by country in Petabytes (PB)

CMIP7 current and projected storage by country in Petabytes (PB)

Staffing resources by country - Full-Time Equivalent (FTE)

* Node has one FTE system administration, and three FTE for regional downscaling, data quality assurance and metadata curation for CMIP7 AFT and CORDEX.

CORDEX CMIP storage

CORDEX CMIP5 current storage by country in Petabytes (PB)

CORDEX CMIP6 current storage by country in Petabytes (PB)

CORDEX CMIP7 AFT projected storage by country in Petabytes (PB)

Comments and Feedback

Near-Term Risks — funding and staff/resources are the most prominent concerns, alongside hardware provisioning and delayed timelines:

- *Risks are that CMIP7 storage isn't funded (properly). Currently awaiting results of national funding round. We have no on-going funding; it is all award/grant funding. The primary funding body is currently funded until mid-2027 and we are awaiting news on an extension.*
- *Currently very low risk.*
- *Due to proposed cuts in funding that affect staff resources.*
- *Current operation probably w/o risk. But CORDEX-CMIP6 is much delayed and may only be ready at a time when we lack qualified persons to continue operation.*
- *There are no immediate risks. However, we anticipate that technical support for node operations may be required in the future.*
- *Currently, there are no notable near-term risks to node operations.*
- *Hardware and staff are not yet provisioned.*
- *Institutional Policy Changes and Staff Resources.*
- *The administration does not seem to fully recognise the importance of operating the ESGF node, and there is no continuous and dedicated funding or personnel investment.*

Capacity for WCRP Projects — government funding and specific storage targets stand out, with the ESGF node construction and national infrastructure proposals as key themes:

- *None open/known future, but one is currently pending review from gov funding body*
- *Yes, there is opportunity to increase.*
- *Through government funding, the total storage capacity can increase to 1 PB in the following years.*
- *Yes. We have a plan to increase our storage capacity by an additional 2PB over the next 2-3 years, supported by a government R&D funding stream.*
- *We may be able to increase capacity by reallocating unused storage.*
- *Not currently for this server.*
- *Yes, we have active opportunities to increase capacity. We are currently submitting a proposal for institutional infrastructure upgrades and seeking additional national research funding for 2026-2027. This initiative aims to expand our storage by an additional 500 TB to 1 PB to fully support the CMIP7-AFT and other WCRP projects.*
- *Yes. We hope that WCRP can formally issue a document requesting support for the construction and operation of a stronger ESGF node.*

CORDEX comments — Focussed on storage scale terms with ESGF-NG publication and funding as recurring themes:

- *As for the CORDEX-CMIP6, only CORDEX-CMIP7-AFT simulations will be shared through our node. The node is not yet online, we are still waiting for the actual machine that will host it, the delivery was greatly delayed.*
- *Additional storage mentioned (500TB) is mainly for replication purpose including CORDEX-CMIP6 or CORDEX-CMIP7-AFT. Could be more depending on data curation on CMIP6 replicas.*
- *We would be willing to host CORDEX-CMIP7 data, if we have storage left. But as stated, our storage amount is very limited anyway.*
- *Our answers depend on funding which has not yet been obtained, but they represent our aim and best estimate.*
- *Our CORDEX-CMIP6 data is accessible by HTTP but not officially published. This data can be published when moving to ESGF-NG. For CORDEX-CMIP6 we have currently generated ~800TB of data and expect to potentially have as much as another PB.*
- *There are internal discussions about if we can commit to this given our current storage limitations so we cannot commit to providing additional storage externally.*
- *We work on contracts, if someone is willing to pay, we can host significant amounts of CORDEX-CMIP6 data e.g. 1PB*
- *We are pleased to support CORDEX-CMIP7-AFT with a tentative allocation of 400 TB. However, this commitment is subject to further discussion regarding technical specifications, data transfer protocols, and long-term maintenance requirements. We look forward to receiving more details on specific agreements.*

Thank You

ipoc@cordex.org

<https://cordex.org>

[@wcrp-cmip.org](https://twitter.com/wcrp-cmip.org)

[wcrp-cmip](https://www.linkedin.com/company/wcrp-cmip)

cmip-ipo@esa.int